

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

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THE BANKING SYSTEM AND ITS ROLE IN ACHIEVING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN IRAQ (ANALYTICAL STUDY)

Abstract.

The banking system, through the work of banks, has a major role in achieving economic development in various countries, whether developing or developed countries, through the financing methods provided by banks to various productive sectors in the country for economic development. Many developed countries consider the development of banking activity in them one of the basic indicators to measure the development in economic activities through increasing banking awareness among individuals, represented by individuals depositing their money and savings with banks, i.e. increasing public confidence in banks, and this is due to the economic, political, security and stable conditions of the country. Investment of that money by banks by lending it to individuals and other institutions with a certain interest, especially in financing investment projects and within an agreed period of time, and this means achieving Economic development in the country, especially if these loans are used in productive investment projects. Therefore, it can be said that banks contribute to achieving economic development through their contribution to the formation of GDP, but the percentage of their contribution is low in Iraq compared to developed countries because the gross domestic product in Iraq depends largely on the contribution of the revenues of the oil sector in its formation as a rentier country and the productivity of its other sectors are almost suspended due to the conditions of the problems experienced by Iraq. Therefore, we recommend activating the role of banks in Iraq by increasing banking awareness among members of society and encouraging individuals to deposit and borrow from banks and using these loans to finance productive economic investment projects through banks' selection of good projects and financing them in order to achieve the economic development of the country.

Keywords . Banking System, Rasheed Bank, Rafidain Bank, Iraq.

Introduction.

Banks have a major and important role in the process of economic development through financing various economic sectors, especially in light of globalization, banks have recently witnessed great developments in their work in order to provide banking services as best as possible and at the lowest possible cost and as soon as possible through the use of modern technology and its application to the work of banks in order to increase the confidence of individuals in banks and increase their dealings with the banking system and deposit their money with banks instead of saving and hoarding their money with them and this means that Banks are working to distribute their financial resources in various areas of investment through deposits they have by members of society and keep part of these resources in the form of reserve cash balances to face emergency situations, so it can be said that all that has increased the efficiency of banking work led to attracting deposits by members of society and then refinancing them through credit activity towards productive projects, and this in turn works to increase domestic production and reduce unemployment rates and thus achieve development economic in the country.

Research hypothesis

The research proceeds from the following hypothesis that the banking system through the work of banks and the Central Bank of Iraq has an important and essential role in stimulating investment opportunities and working to increase them and thus achieve economic development in Iraq.

Search problem.

The problem of the research is that there are problems in the country that affected the performance of the banking sector in financing investment projects and thus negatively affected the achievement of economic development in Iraq.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the research are the following points:

1. I am a man of the same age Study and analyze the work of banks and their importance in achieving economic development in Iraq through the positive impact on GDP and other economic variables that work to achieve economic development in Iraq.

2. Study and analysis of loans and deposits provided by Iraqi banks in achieving economic development.

The importance of research.

The importance of the research is to know the role played by banks in achieving economic development in Iraq through loans and deposits with banks and how to use these loans to finance productive investment projects in order to achieve economic development in the country.

Search limits

Spatial boundaries. Iraq, Rasheed Bank, and Rafidain Bank.

Time limits. Post-2004 Iraq data.

Research Methodology

In order to prove the validity of the hypothesis from which the research was launched, the descriptive

analysis approach was adopted through the analysis of data related to banks and economic development in Iraq, and then we reached the conclusion, which includes a sentence of conclusions and recommendations.

The banking system and its role in achieving economic development in Iraq after 2004

Here in this topic, the reality of the banking system in Iraq is studied and analyzed through the work of banks by taking a sample of banks, which are represented by Al-Rasheed Bank and Rafidain Bank and their role in achieving economic development in Iraq and can be addressed as follows :

1.1. Banks in Iraq and their role in achieving economic development in Iraq after 2004.

The role played by banks in achieving economic development in Iraq has become important and essential for the Iraqi government, if the Iraqi government confirmed it through the preparation of annual development plans in order to achieve the development process of the country, especially since Iraq has gone through very difficult circumstances that affected the reality of economic development in it, the emergence of globalization and developments that have occurred in the world have appeared significant changes to the services provided by banks as a result of the development in the world, such as interest in the application of performance standards and standards Financial technology and increasing the contribution to the formation of the country's GDP through the availability of funds for investment and increasing investment in various economic productive sectors of the country.⁽²⁾

The banks are working to stimulate savings and increase it through the deposit of deposits in banks and link those savings to economic investment projects and achieve an economic return development at the country level, hence the importance of banks and their role through financing in order to provide financial resources to get rid of the gap between the increasing demand for investment and limited savings in the Iraqi economy as there is a great demand for bank financing by individuals and institutions, which in turn affects the reality of economic development in Iraq In a very large way, it has recently appeared that there are more than (75) countries that have banking institutions that contain these countries on more than (292) banks in order to conduct banking transactions, and there are many methods that financial institutions and banks can use in financing operations, and these methods are represented by two important types, namely financing methods on the basis of sharing the return on investment, first, and secondly, through financing methods based on debt, and thirdly, it depends on financing methods that are based on participation. In the return on investment, i.e. speculation, it is one of the most common methods in the work of banks, especially commercial banks.

The bank credit granted by banks varies in terms of its long term, whether it is long-term, mediumterm or short-term, as well as differs in terms of its purpose and in terms of guarantees provided in order to obtain it in order to finance the productive sectors or cover the needs of individuals and institutions, and the political, economic and security conditions and problems experienced by Iraq from the occupation and war of ISIS and the Corona pandemic led to reducing opportunities for economic development in Iraq at the present time and that matter It negatively affects the reality and goals of economic development to be achieved until 2030 due to the global economic problems that hit the economies of the entire world as a result of the Corona pandemic, but achieving economic development in Iraq requires the adoption of economic policies represented in the following:

1. Promoting and stimulating government investment policies by achieving the goals of economic development in the country through education and health, ensuring social justice, ensuring the distribution of investment at the local level, adopting large economic projects that support economic development, as well as activating the role of the private sector in the country by strengthening partnership and work between the public sector and the private sector for the purpose of stimulating investment in various fields and various sectors, and this stimulus is through financing by Iraqi banks.(4)

- 2 . Formulating development programs aimed at achieving integration and balance and working to stimulate investment spending.

3. Work on the development of infrastructure that is of high quality in order to promote economic development programs.

4. Take laws and decisions that lead to the efficiency of the planning process to achieve economic development in Iraq.

Here in this research we will take a sample of the banks represented by Rafidain Bank and Rasheed Bank and can be addressed as follows.

1.1.1. Rafidain Bank in Iraq .

It is the first Iraqi commercial bank established in Iraq under Law No. 33 of 1941 and began its work on 19/5/1941 and was the beginning of its work with a capital of (50) million Iraqi dinars, the credit activity is one of the investment operations carried out by Rafidain Bank, as well as financing various sectors and investing money in accordance with economic policies in order to achieve economic development in Iraq, as the activity and services of Rafidain Bank are represented by providing the smart card, Selling dollars to individuals, providing advances and loans to individuals and institutions, bank credit, and opening a current account.

Loans and Deposits with Rafidain Bank in Iraq for the Period 2004-2020 (Million Iraqi Dinars)

Years	Loans	Deposits
2004	1173239287	7274508133
2005	129188309	6310612011
2006	122250429	9338694391
2007	259649137	15664458139
2008	689202173	22022703946
2009	1136191799	19223802909
2010	3579192308	24235827970
2011	7486561094	26950651508
2012	11466033626	29457425907
2013	6350947937	2274278616
2014	12517345711	34047613298
2015	12322490531	31127527678
2016	6350947937	227478616
2017	12343348525	30116331694
2018	12387448961	34696359047
2019	13301129232	27932489621
2020	13311128242	28732478632

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Bureau of Statistics, Analytical financial indicators of banking and insurance activity for the public and private sectors for the period 2004-2020.

Figure 1: Loans and deposits with Rafidain Bank in Iraq for the period 2004-2020 (million Iraqi dinars)

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (1) through the use of the program (Excel).

From the above table, we note that the loans provided by Rafidain Bank were low in 2004, 2005, 2006 as a result of the difficult circumstances that the country went through as a result of regime change, but in 2007 and 2008 loans began to rise, due to the improvement of the general situation of the country, whether political or economic, as the loans of Rafidain Bank for the year 2007 amounted to approximately (7 3 1 9 4 6 9 5 2) Iraqi dinars and loans during 2008 Approximately (3 7 1 2 0 2 9 8 6) Iraqi dinars as shown in the table above.

In 2010, Rafidain Bank granted loans to employees, and this led to an increase in loans provided by the bank and became approximately (8 0 3 2 9 1 9 7 5 3) Iraqi dinars, and in 2014-2015, due to the entry of ISIS into Iraq, it led to a decrease in loans provided by banks, as it became approximately (11754371521) Iraqi dinars during 2014 and approximately (12517345711) Iraqi dinars during 2015. As shown in Table 1, then loans be-

gan to rise gradually during 2019 and 2020 to reach approximately (2 3 2 9 2 1 1 0 3 3 1) dinars during the year 2019 and (13311128242) dinars during the year 2020, because the bank granted loans to all segments of employees in order to improve their social status, The loans provided to institutions and investment entrepreneurs with regard to Rafidain Bank deposits, which were low During the years 2004, 2005 and 2006, it amounted to (3 3 1 8 0 5 4 7 2 7) Iraqi dinars during the year 2004 and amounted to approximately (1 9 3 4 9 6 8 3 3 9) Iraqi dinars during the year 2006, which are low amounts as a result of the difficult economic conditions and problems experienced by the country during those years, which affected the public's confidence in the bank as well as led to a lack of awareness. Banking with individuals and institutions in Iraq during the three years mentioned above, and then deposits with Rafidain Bank began to rise during the years 2007 2008 2009 in order to improve the country's political, economic and

security conditions and this means increasing the confidence of individuals in the bank and the government as we note that the public's confidence in banks is linked to the economic, security and political conditions of the country, the more good the conditions, the more confidence of individuals in banks and this means depositing their money in banks instead of hoarding or saving them with them We note from Table 1 The amount of deposits with Rafidain Bank began to increase during the years 2017 2018, 2019 due to the improvement of the security and political conditions of the economy and because of the gradual improvement of the country's conditions and we note from the table that

the percentage of gross domestic product in Iraq depends very much on the export of oil only and the import of goods and services from abroad in addition to that it is witnessing a halt to other economic sectors such as agriculture, industry, trade and other sectors that have a contribution to the formation of domestic product For example, in 2004 the proportion of crude oil in the composition of GDP was approximately 95.57% while industry was 75.1% is a very low percentage and the rest of the other sectors also constituted very low percentages that do not exceed (10%).⁽⁵⁾

We note from the following table that the GDP ratios in Iraq from loans and deposits to Rafidain Bank are very low rates as shown in the following table:

Table (2)

GDP Ratios of Loans and Deposits (Rafidain Bank) In Iraq for the period 2004-2020 million dinars

Years	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	GDP Ratios from Loans 100%	GDP Percentage of Deposits 100%
2004	47959000	4.08	0.65
2005	73533000	56.91	1.16
2006	95588000	78.19	1.02
2007	111455813	42.92	0.71
2008	157026062	22.78	0.71
2009	130642187	11.49	0.67
2010	167099204	4.66	0.68
2011	217327107	2.90	0.80
2012	254225490	2.21	0.86
2013	273587529	4.30	12.02
2014	258900633	2.06	0.76
2015	191715791	1.55	0.61
2016	171490000	2.70	75.38
2017	464701138	3.76	1.54
2018	251064500	2.02	0.72
2019	223412523	1.67	0.79
2020	213422122	1.60	0.74

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (1) and the first column of Table (2).

This means that banks have a role in achieving economic development through GDP and other economic variables, but in Iraq their contribution is very small and low, since the gross domestic product in Iraq depends in its composition on the oil sector, as we mentioned earlier, and that loans granted by banks are not used to finance investment projects because investment projects mean increasing domestic production and

means the optimal use of economic resources and means reducing unemployment rates and thus achieving economic development in the country Rather, loans are used for non-productive and non-investment projects, and if they are non-investment, they are unprofitable, so the projects must be studied by banks so that the loans granted to these projects are feasible and work to achieve the economic development of the country.

Figure (2) GDP Ratios of Loans and Deposits (Rafidain Bank) in Iraq for the Period 2004-2020

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (2) through the use of the program (Excel).
1 - 1-2. Rasheed Bank in Iraq.

One of the most important Iraqi banks that was established during 1988 and is the second and largest government bank in Iraq this bank to invest money and provide financing and provide other banking services in order to support and achieve economic development in Iraq by supporting the Iraqi economy in its various sectors through loans provided to all economic sectors, individuals and institutions and that its capital reached

one billion Iraqi dinars in 2001 and there are many services provided by the bank are as follows: - (7) Draft resolution

- 1- Advances and loans.
- 2- Granting credit facilities.
- 3- Open a current account.
- 4- Accepting deposits of all kinds, as shown in the following table:

Table No. (3)

Loans and deposits with Al-Rasheed Bank in Iraq for the period 2004-2020
Million Iraqi Dinars

Years	Loans	Deposits
2004	45292606	2895508893
2005	42289665	2594621722
2006	40487808	1283600000
2007	127099294	3179303712
2008	278293402	4755991200
2009	433497542	8061337181
2010	915661329	11436995320
2011	5829228810	1283600000
2012	3726295853	15070728345
2013	468042216	5323592899
2014	5829228810	1283600000
2015	5557125430	14534386672
2016	4846289557	52784503775
2017	4564010767	14257907303
2018	4722906665	16454847047
2019	5829228810	15514807205
2020	5829228810	15514807205

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Bureau of Statistics, Analytical financial indicators of banking and insurance activity for the public and private sectors for the period 2004-2020.

As we mentioned before, between loans and deposits depend on the security and political conditions of the country. The more independent those conditions are, the greater the public's confidence in the bank and

the Iraqi government. This means that individuals deposit their money and savings with banks, and therefore the bank grants these deposits in the form of loans of different kinds by facilitating investment operations for

projects, institutions and individuals. This has a big role in achieving economic development in Iraq. Financing investment projects means increasing productivity and increasing GDP. Achieving high levels of employment also means achieving the economic development of the country, and this is achieved in the event of stability of the economic, security and political conditions in Iraq. We note from Table (3) that the GDP ratios of loans

and deposits of Al-Rasheed Bank are very low during the study period, and as shown in the table, except for the period from 2004-2008, the percentage of output from loans was high compared to other years, and this means that the GDP was much greater than the loans granted during the period 2004-

2008. (6) Introduction of the Protocol.

Shape (3) Loans and deposits with Al-Rasheed Bank in Iraq for the period 2004-2020

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (3) through the use of the program (Excel).

Table (4)

GDP Ratios of Loans and Deposits (Rasheed Bank) for the Period 2004-2020 Million JD

Years	GDP Ratios from Loans	GDP Percentage of Deposits
	100%	100%
2004	105.88	1.656323699
2005	173.87	2.834054744
2006	236.09	7.446868183
2007	87.69	3.505667376
2008	56.42	3.301647446
2009	30.13	1.620601943
2010	18.24	1.461041115
2011	3.72	16.93106162
2012	6.82	1.686882572
2013	58.45	5.139151964
2014	4.44	20.16988415
2015	3.44	1.31904975
2016	3.53	0.324887017
2017	10.18	3.259252064
2018	5.31	1.525778388
2019	3.83	1.439995483
2020	3.66	1.375602798

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (3) and the first column of Table (2).

Figure (4) GDP Ratios of Loans and Deposits (Al-Rasheed Bank) for the period 2004-2020

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (4) through the use of the program (Excel).

1-2 . Banking indicators that stimulate economic development in Iraq.

There are banking indicators that stimulate economic growth in Iraq, such indicators are as follows:

(1).

1. Banking Credit Activity:

Credit activity is a major and important indicator to achieve economic development in Iraq and this can be achieved through the following points:

A- Expanding the granting of bank credit to the private sector, as the percentage of the total credit granted to the private sector in the total bank credit reached approximately (52%) during 2020, while the percentage was (50%) during 2019.

B- Supervising the banking system in order to achieve the required objectives.

2 .Banking Performance Measurement

Index:

With regard to the indicator of measuring banking performance, it can be measured through the efficiency of capital performance and the liquidity ratio, the capital adequacy ratio reached (15%) for Rafidain Bank during the year 2020, and that percentage exceeds the standard ratio of (12%). While Al-Rasheed Bank has a capital adequacy ratio of approximately (11%), which is less than the standard ratio, and this means that the bank is exposed to risk.

3 .Indicator of raising the banking density.

It means the increase in the number of branches of private banks and government banks and can be explained as follows:

a. The number of branches of operating government banks reached during 2020 approximately (150) branches in Baghdad, while it was (140) branches during 2019.

b. The number of branches of government banks operating in the governorates reached approximately (279) branches during 2020, which is equal to the number of branches during 2019.

c. The number of private banks operating during 2020 reached approximately (174) branches in Baghdad, while the number of branches reached (169) branches during 2019.

d. The number of private banks operating in the governorates reached approximately (455) branches during 2020 compared to (454) branches during 2019.

4. Improving the services of the banking sector.

The banking sector services are upgraded through the modernization of electronic payment systems because they are one of the important measures on which to measure the degree of development of the banking system in Iraq and that electronic payment systems are as follows:

a. Directing all banks and licensees to provide mobile banking application service in accordance with the strategy of the Central Bank in order to improve banking services and achieve financial inclusion. ⁽⁸⁾

b. The total online payment recorded approximately 63% via mobile phone.

c. An increase in the number of expenditure units for employees whose salaries are domiciled in banks, as it reached approximately (6 7 0 2) spending units during the year 2020 for approximately (9 8 5 7 6 8) employees .

f. As for the preparation of open bank accounts, the preparation of electronic cards, the preparation of the scope of sale, the preparation of withdrawal points, the preparation of electronic wallets, and the preparation of ATMs, as I mentioned according to the report of the Central Bank of Iraq for the year 2020, it can be mentioned as follows:

1- The number of open bank accounts reached (6 9 9 8 2 1 6) accounts and increased from 2019 by 100% completely.

2 - The number of electronic cards was (8 0 4 9 4 7 1 1) cards, while the number of cards during 2019 was equal to (5 2 7 6 0 5 0 1) cards.

3-POS reached (1,0457) points during 2020 as mentioned above, while it reached (6,22,22) points during 2019.

4- The number of POS cash withdrawal points was (6 9 7 9 3 1 points during 2020 while it was equal to (7 7 6 1 1) points during 2019.

5. The number of e-wallets reached (5 3 2 6 22 1) portfolio during 2020 while it reached (7 9 7 3 0 4) portfolio during 2019.

6. The number of ATMs reached (0 4 3 1) during 2020 while it was equal to (4 1 0 1) during 2019.

In order to stimulate the role of the banking sector in activating economic activity and achieving economic development, the Deposit Insurance Company was established, which included private and government banks and foreign banks, which were distributed by (44) banks (22) of which commercial banks and (6) of which government banks and (16) foreign banks that this company has a great and essential role in protecting the banking sector by providing cover to guarantee the deposits of individuals with Iraqi banks, which are licensed by the Central Bank.

1-3. The role of the Central Bank of Iraq in achieving economic development in Iraq.

The Central Bank has an important and main role in solving the economic crises experienced by Iraq and developing solutions to mitigate the social and economic effects of those crises to which Iraq was exposed as follows: **First. Corona Covid 19 pandemic crisis:**

The Central Bank worked to confront this crisis through the following measures:

1. The Central Bank's support, in cooperation with Iraqi banks, has raised approximately (44) million Iraqi dinars during 2020 in order to meet the needs of this health crisis, prevent the spread of this epidemic and provide medical supplies for the purpose of reducing the mortality rate and the high cases of recovery.

2- The Central Bank announced the postponement of the payment of financial installments incurred by the beneficiaries of loans for investment and non-investment projects, stressing the bank not to increase the interest as a result of postponing the payment of installments for a period of six months

3- Postponing the payment of installments for tourism sector projects for a longer period until recovery from the Corona epidemic.

4- Directing the Central Bank to the initiative of one trillion Iraqi dinars and reducing the interest rate to approximately (5.3%) after it was equal to (8.4%) for individual borrowers within the bracket (1 to 20) million Iraqi dinars, as well as reducing the interest from (3.6%) to (4%) for individual borrowers within the bracket (21 million to 1 billion Iraqi dinars).

Second. Oil price news crisis and the impact of the OPEC agreement:

The Central Bank, in conjunction with the Iraqi banking system, worked to finance the financial deficit in its budget in 2020, as treasury transfers to the Central Bank of Iraq, which were issued by the Iraqi Ministry of Finance based on the Foreign and Local Borrowing Law, were deducted during the year 2020 and amounted to approximately (26) trillion Iraqi dinars, as well as according to the decisions of the Board of Directors of the Central Bank No. 184 during the year 2020 There has been a package of reforms to devalue

the exchange rate and achieve macro stability in the economy.

The role of the Central Bank of Iraq is also evident in achieving economic development in Iraq by encouraging and stimulating real investment by stimulating banking credit activity and directing it towards productive and development projects in a way that works to achieve the optimal use of economic resources, reduce unemployment rates, raise productive levels, achieve economic development in various economic sectors of the country and confirm the role of the Central Bank of Iraq in stimulating investment. The Central Bank has continued, through cooperation with Iraqi banks, to provide bank financing and bank credit towards investment projects, during 2015 the Central Bank of Iraq presented an exceptional initiative in order to address the lack of liquidity to address recessions in the Iraqi economy, reduce poverty and unemployment, stimulate economic growth rates, as well as develop and expand productive projects and work on the spread of new projects, the Central Bank has presented an initiative (one trillion Iraqi dinars), the purpose of which is to finance medium and small projects. The total loans provided by the Central Bank of Iraq in 2015 and until 2020 amounted to approximately (8 7 4. 2 2 3) billion Iraqi dinars.

Conclusions and recommendations:

First: Conclusions: The research reached a number of conclusions that can be mentioned in the following points:

1. The banking system in Iraq contributes to achieving economic development, but at a low rate due to the economic, political and security conditions experienced by Iraq.

2. The percentage of the contribution of the banking system in the formation of GDP in Iraq is very low because the GDP depends in its composition on a very large percentage on the oil sector and a very low percentage that may not exceed (10%) as the contribution of other economic sectors in its formation.

3. The volume of deposits with banks by individuals and institutions depends to a very large extent on the security situation and political stability of the country because the loans granted by banks depend on those deposits.

4. The Iraqi banking system contributes to stimulating investment projects through loans granted to those projects, whether medium-term or long-term for the purpose of achieving economic development in Iraq.

5- Bank loans are one of the most important sources of financing for individuals, institutions and projects and have a positive impact on the economic reality of Iraq.

Second: Recommendations:

1. Keep abreast of the Iraqi bank of developments and modern technologies used in the banking system in developed countries.

2. The need for the Iraqi banking system to abide by the instructions and laws of the Central Bank in order to achieve the goal of the Central Bank in achieving economic development in Iraq.

3. Cancel the conditions that hinder some economic projects in order to obtain financial financing by Iraqi banks.

4. Encouraging institutions and individuals to borrow from Iraqi banks and directing those loans towards productive projects in order to achieve economic development in the country through the banking system.

5. Countries contracted with productive projects in Iraq in order to encourage their local product and rely on it without importing from abroad in meeting the local need of the country and thus achieving high levels of production, reducing unemployment rates and raising the percentage of economic sectors in the formation of GDP.

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